

Synthesis of Potential Amoebacides. Part XXI*

A. B. Sen and S. B. Singh

Several substituted $\beta\beta$ -bis-aminoalkyl-2,6-dipropionylphenols (I) have been synthesised as potential amoebacides.

In recent years the alkaloid conessine and the antibiotic tetracycline have received great importance as amoebacides. The significant feature of conessine molecule is the presence of two tertiary nitrogen atoms, bridged through a chain of nine carbon atoms, whereas the activity of tetracyclines is ascribed to chelating $-\text{OH}$ and $-\text{CO}$ groups in their molecule.

In the present investigation, the compounds of the type (I) having the combined characteristic features of conessine and tetracycline molecules have been synthesised expecting their antiamoebic activity. The synthesis involves the Mannich reaction on substituted 2, 6-diacetylphenols and the subsequent double Fries migration of the appropriate phenols, furnishing the diketones.

After single Fries migration, acetylation of the resultant 2-hydroxyacetophenones proved difficult. After trials of the various known methods, the acetyl chloride-pyridine method provided good yields of the acetates. In all, the acetates of three substituted phenolic ketones (vide Experimental) were prepared and then these were subjected to a second Fries migration with anhydrous aluminium chloride.

EXPERIMENTAL

5-Chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone was prepared by the method of Auwers and Wittig¹.

5-Methyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone was prepared by the method of Rosenmund and Schnurr²,

*The number of part refers to the series "Possible Antiamoebic Agents". Ed,

1. *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 1270.

2. *Annalen*, 1926, 460, 56,

4,6-Dimethyl-5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone was obtained by the Fries rearrangement of 3,5 dimethyl-4-chlorophenyl acetate (0.1M) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.15M) at 120-30° for 2 hr. and recrystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 94°, yield 90%. (Found: C 60.10; H, 4.90. C₁₀H₁₁O₂Cl requires C, 60.60; H 5.55%).

Acetylation of Substituted 2-Hydroxyacetophenones^{3,4}.—To a well-cooled solution of the appropriate hydroxyacetophenone (0.1M) in dry pyridine (5 parts, w/w) was added acetyl chloride (0.3M) dropwise with stirring and cooling. The products were isolated in the usual way and characterised through their 2,4 DNPs.

5-Methyl-2-acetoxyacetophenone was obtained in very low yields by the above method and was therefore prepared as follows. To dry potassium salt of 5-methyl 2-hydroxyacetophenone (from 0.1M hydroxyketone and 0.15M-KOH in water and then evaporating to dryness) was added acetyl chloride (0.3M) dropwise with stirring and cooling. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual to provide the pure product; b.p. 83-86 /6mm, yield 40%. The b.p., yield, and analysis of the compounds are reported in Table I.

TABLE I

Sl. No	Substitution in A.	Yield.	B.P.	Found.	Reqd.	2,4-DNP (mono).		Reqd.
						M.P.	Found.	
1	R=Cl; X ₁ =X ₂ =H	80%	113-15°/6mm	C : 56.21% H : 3.90	56.48% 4.24	263°	N : 14.05%	14.37%
2	R=Me; X ₁ =X ₂ =H	40	83-80°/6	C : 68.90 H : 5.95	68.75 6.25	266°	N : 14.85	15.06
3	R=Cl; X ₁ =X ₂ =Me	86	110-13°/5	C : 59.23 H : 5.10	59.88 5.41		..	..

2,6-Diacetyl-4-alkylphenols were obtained by the Fries migration of the acetates of substituted 2-hydroxyacetophenones. An intimate mixture of the acetate (0.1M) and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.33M) was heated at 130° for 1 hr. and then at 140° for 1 hr. The products isolated in the usual way were characterised through their 2,4-DNPs.

The acetate of 4,6-dimethyl-5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone required heating at 130° for 2 hr. and at 140-50° for 1 hr. for its rearrangement. The yields of the diketones obtained, their b.p., m.p., and analysis are recorded in Table II.

3. Hickingbottom, "Reactions of Organic Compounds", p. 120.

4. Bhatt and Shah, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 318.

TABLE II

(B)

Sl. No.	Substitution in B.	Yield.	D.P. or M.P.	Found.	Reqd.	M.P.	2,4-DNP (di).	
							Found.	Reqd.
1.	R = Cl; X ₁ = X ₂ = H	80%	120°/6mm.	C : 57.21% H : 4.90	56.48% 4.24	246°	N : 10.23%	19.56%
2.	R = Me; X ₁ = X ₂ = H	70	85-87°/5	C : 68.15 H : 5.61	68.75 6.25	257-59°	N : 20.40	20.29
3.	R = Cl; X ₁ = X ₂ = Me	75	94°	C : 59.20 H : 4.90	59.88 5.41	..	..	..

Mannich Bases

Mannich bases of 2,6-diaceto-4-substituted phenol and 3,5-dimethyl-4-chloro-2,6-diacetophenol were prepared according to the method of Elmer and Hoftmeister⁵. A mixture of the diketone (0.025M), amine or amine hydrochlorid (0.1M), and paraformaldehyde (0.06M) was taken in sufficient absolute ethanol (20 ml) and saturated with dry HCl gas and then refluxed on a water bath for 1-2 hr. Further paraformaldehyde (0.05M) was added and the mixture refluxed again for 5-6 hr. After cooling, the Mannich base hydrochloride was filtered. A further quantity was obtained by working up the filtrate. The Mannich base hydrochlorides are listed in Table III.

TABLE III

Sl. No.	Substituted phenol.	Amine.	Mannich base hydrochlorides.				Dipicrates.			
			Formula.	Yield.	M.P.	%Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.	M.P.	%Nitrogen. Found. Reqd.		
1.	R = Cl; X ₁ = X ₂ = H	NEt ₂	C ₂₀ H ₃₅ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₃	35%	225°	5.92	6.15	..	..	..
		Piperidine	C ₂₂ H ₃₅ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₃	48	181°	5.60	5.84	158-60°	12.41	12.95
		Morpholine	C ₂₀ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₃	60	159-60°	5.47	5.79	167°	12.62	12.90
2.	R = Me; X ₁ = X ₂ = H	NEt ₂	C ₂₁ H ₃₅ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₂	30	220-222°	6.82	6.44	..	..	..
		Piperidine	C ₂₃ H ₃₅ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₂	50	155°	5.90	6.10	..	..	..
		Morpholine	C ₂₁ H ₃₂ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₂	62	138-40°	6.35	6.05	..	..	..
3.	R = Cl; X ₁ = X ₂ = Me	NEt ₂	C ₂₂ H ₃₇ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₃	32	225°	5.52	5.70	..	..	..
		Piperidine	C ₂₄ H ₃₇ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₃	48	258°	5.12	5.52	..	..	..

Mannich base hydrochlorides of *o*-aceto-*p*-chloro-*m*-cresol were obtained in the usual way. A mixture of 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-6-methylacetophenone, amine, and paraformaldehyde (0.01*M* each) in absolute ethanol (20-30 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 4-5 hr. after saturating it with dry HCl gas. After cooling, the Mannich base hydrochloride was filtered. The Mannich base hydrochlorides are listed in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Sl No.	Amino.	Formula.	Mannich base hydrochlorides.		Picrates.				
			Yield.	M.P.	%Nitrogen.		M.P.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.		Found.	Reqd.
1.	Piperidine	$C_{13}H_{21}O_2NCl_2$	55%	100°	4.12	4.39	180°	10.54	10.97
2.	Morpholine	$C_{14}H_{19}O_3NCl_2$	00	160°	5.04	4.37	185°	10.48	10.93

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